

Supporting information

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1 Simulation of cell to module losses

Upscaling losses going from cell to a module are quantified through an equivalent circuit of a perovskite module device, using Simulation Program with Integrated Circuit Emphasis (SPICE) based modeling. In the model, perovskite based module is represented by the equivalent circuit as shown in the module cross section shown in Figure S1.^[1;2;3;4;5]

Module is represented by serial connection of cells with length of 5 mm and a lateral resolution of 50 μm . The electrical parameters of the single diode model have been extracted by fitting experimental data of 0.13 cm^2 perovskite device. As indicated a cell is divided into two parts: the active area, w_a and the dead, inactive area, w_d . Inactive area represents the area needed for the cell to cell interconnection, that typically consists of three patterns: P1, P2 and P3 as indicated. P1 and P3 are used as isolation steps to interrupt the front and back contact respectively, so that the photo generated current of the cell would be collected and transferred to the next cell through an ohmic contact at pattern P2.

Upscaling from cell to module introduces four loss mechanisms: sheet resistance loss; interconnection area loss; interconnection resistance loss and layer inhomogeneity loss. Assuming, all ideal, homogeneous and uniform layers, defined loss mechanisms are integrated into model shown in the Figure S1 as follows:

- sheet resistance loss depending on R_{ITO} and R_{Au} , representing sheet resistance of front and back electrodes and the cell length^[2];
- interconnection area loss, represented by ratio of the inactive area length (w_d) to full cell length ($w_a + w_d$) and

- interconnection resistance loss, represented by resistance at the ohmic contact of front and back electrode at the P2 pattern, R_{P2} ^[6].

The simulated module performance is compared to the results for a single cell. Since layer inhomogeneity losses are not represented in this model, all other cell to module losses not quantified through this model are assumed to be due to the layer inhomogeneity loss.

2 Temporal variations in luminescence imaging

Electroluminescence and micro photoluminescence spectroscopy used for step 2 and 3 within the characterization method of this study (Figure S2) depends on the luminescence behavior of perovskite based solar cells. Multiple studies report a variation of luminescence in EL and PL intensity of perovskite solar cells over the time frame of seconds to minutes.^[7;8;9;10;11;12] This characteristic has been interpreted as an effect of ionic nature of perovskite semiconductor that can hinder quantitative analysis of luminescence imaging.^[9] Samples analyzed in this study exhibit significant variation in luminescence in the time frame of tens of minutes when kept at a constant forward bias for a period of 30 mins (Figure S3a). The difference in EL intensity of different cells in the module can be significant even after minutes of measurement and stabilize across full module after more than 10 minutes. Aside from the luminescence changes affected by dynamics of ionic species, macroscopic layer inhomogeneity features do not change over time and are visible in all EL images. However, in order to compare layer inhomogeneities visible with different samples, the discussed images are acquired after 30 mins of constant voltage bias.

Moreover, during PL spot measurements temporal variation in PL intensity, peak position and width is recorded for a period of 20 minutes. The variation in PL signal is reversible and fully recovers when samples are kept at open circuit in dark for a period of 40 minutes (Figure S3b). Similar to electroluminescence, the variation in photoluminescence has been assigned to the ionic nature of perovskite^[11] and not related to perovskite degradation, taking into account reversibility of the response and device encapsulation. In the further analysis we will focus on PL full module maps and local maps, which represent a snapshot of photoluminescence response.

References

- [1] S. Eidelloth, F. Haase, R. Brendel, IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics 2012, 2, 572.

REFERENCES

- [2] B. Turan, S. Haas, *Journal of Laser Micro/Nanoengineering* 2013, 8, DOI 10.2961/jlmn.2013.03.0009.
- [3] H. Hoppe, M. Seeland, B. Muhsin, *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 2012, 97, 119.
- [4] R. Gehlhaar, T. Merckx, C. Masse de la Huerta, L. Rakocevic, W. Qiu, M. Jaysankar (2016). *Loss Analysis and Optimization for High Efficiency Perovskite Photovoltaic Modules*. EUPVSEC, Amsterdam.
- [5] H. Higuchi, T. Negami, *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.* 2018, 57, 08RE11.
- [6] L. Rakocevic, R. Gehlhaar, T. Merckx, W. Qiu, U. W. Paetzold, H. Fledderus, J. Poortmans, *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics* 2017, 7, 404.
- [7] B. Chen, J. Peng, H. Shen, T. Duong, D. Walter, S. Johnston, M. M. Al-Jassim, K. J. Weber, T. P. White, K. R. Catchpole, D. Macdonald, H. T. Nguyen, *Advanced Energy Materials* 2018, 9, 1802790.
- [8] A. M. Soufiani, Z. Hameiri, S. Meyer, S. Lim, M. J. Y. Tayebjee, J. S. Yun, A. Ho-Baillie, G. J. Conibeer, L. Spiccia, M. A. Green, *Advanced Energy Materials* 2017, 7, 1602111.
- [9] A. M. Soufiani, J. Kim, A. Ho-Baillie, M. Green, Z. Hameiri, *Advanced Energy Materials* 2018, 8, 1702256.
- [10] M. Okano, M. Endo, A. Wakamiya, M. Yoshita, H. Akiyama, Y. Kanemitsu, *Appl. Phys. Express* 2015, 8, 102302.
- [11] A. Walter, S. Moon, B. A. Kamino, L. Lofgren, D. Sacchetto, F. Matteocci, B. Taheri, J. Bailat, A. D. Carlo, C. Ballif, S. Nicolay, *IEEE Journal of Photovoltaics* 2018, 8, 151.
- [12] Y. Wu, H. Shen, D. Walter, D. Jacobs, T. Duong, J. Peng, L. Jiang, Y.-B. Cheng, K. Weber, *Advanced Functional Materials* 2016, 26, 6807.

Figure S 1: Module cross-section showing one cell in a module with active area and interconnection. Perovskite module equivalent circuit used for simulation is shown overlaying the module cross-section for better understanding of the purpose of each of the circuit elements.

Figure S 2: Process used to characterize devices is explained in five steps. Step 1 represents JV and MPPT measurements. Step 2, 3 and 4 are imaging techniques EL, DLIT and μ PLS. Step 5 is electron microscopy analysis where SEM, EDX and FIB are applied.

Figure S 3: a) EL intensity change of a spin coated module and its cells during 30 minutes forward voltage bias. EL images of the module after 0.5, 10, 20 and 30 minutes of constant applied voltage bias. b) PL intensity reversible change during spot measurement for period of 20 mins, showing recovery time of 10s of minutes necessary for the sample to return to initial state.

Figure S 4: Hysteresis J-V sweep and maximum power point tracking result for a) spin coated and b) blade coated modules analyzed in the study. Black lines are measurements of best cell devices for spin coated and blade coated devices respectively.

Figure S 5: a) Spin coated module with type 5 inhomogeneity clearly visible in EL. SEM cross sections of bright luminescence b) and dark luminescence c) area showing the difference in left over organic PCBM layer in c).

Figure S 6: Characterization of 100 cm² module presented in Figure 7c-e, where in a) EL image after 10 minutes at 16 V voltage bias. The limitation in setup did not allow applying voltage bias comparable to V_{OC} or forward voltage bias. b) DLIT image at 20 V bias. c) μ PLS intensity map showing 18 out of 20 serially connected cells in a module.